

The Role of Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Toughening Mechanisms in DGEBA Fracture

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Why Composites?

- ✓ Lighter than Metals
- ✓ Corrosion & Chemical Resistance
- ✓ Less fatigue Issues
- ✓ Tailorable Microstructure

Challenge: Improving toughness of brittle polymer resins in CFRC's

Classical Fracture Mechanics

Mode I
Fracture

Mode II
Fracture

Mode III
Fracture

Dynamic Fracture Challenges

Inertia considered through equations of motion

Rapidly evolving crack tip

Transient wave interactions

No ASTM standard for dynamic fracture!

Key Parameters: Material acceleration, dilatational and distortional wave speeds, and crack tip velocity

Experimental Configuration

Experimental Parameters

Camera	Shimadzu HPV-X
Frame Rate	1M FPS
Interframe Time	1 μ s
Resolution	400 x 250

Elastodynamic Solution: u -SIF Relations

$$u_x(r, \theta) = \frac{2K_I}{\mu R(v) \sqrt{2\pi}} \left\{ (1 + \alpha_S^2) r_L^{1/2} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_L}{2}\right) - 2\alpha_1 \alpha_2 r_S^{1/2} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_S}{2}\right) \right\}$$

$$u_y(r, \theta) = \frac{2\alpha_L K_I}{\mu R(v) \sqrt{2\pi}} \left\{ (1 + \alpha_S^2) r_L^{1/2} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_L}{2}\right) - 2r_S^{1/2} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_S}{2}\right) \right\}$$

$$R(v) = 4\alpha_1 \alpha_2 - (1 + \alpha_2^2) \quad \alpha_L = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c_L^2} \quad r_L = \sqrt{x^2 - \alpha_L^2 y^2}$$

$$\theta_L = \arctan(\alpha_L \tan \theta)$$

$$\theta_S = \arctan(\alpha_S \tan \theta) \quad \alpha_S = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c_S^2} \quad r_S = \sqrt{x^2 - \alpha_S^2 y^2}$$

Dependent on velocity at crack tip

HOMOGENEOUS TOUGHENING: Amine hardeners effect on toughness

Dynamic Fracture Results: DGEBA/D400

DGEBA Amine Agent	Glass Transition T_g , [C]	Young's Modulus E , [MPa]	Density ρ , [g/m ³]	Quasi-static Fracture Toughness K_{IC} , [MPa m ^{1/2}]	Dilatational Wave Speed C_L , [m/s]	Shear Wave Speed C_s , [m/s]
D400	50	2556±170	1152	1.5± 0.2	1.49	0.81
D230	100	3070±140	1161	0.8± 0.1	1.63	0.39
PACM	160	2180±140	1125	0.8± 0.1	1.39	0.46

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Results for Quasi-static and Dynamic

HETEROGENEOUS TOUGHENING: Glass Particulates in DGEBA Binder

3 Bead Volumes: 5, 15, 30%

Bead Type	Mean Bead Size (μm)	Density (g/cc)	Young's Modulus (MPa)
Spheriglass A-3000	30-50	1.59	10
Spheriglass A-5000	7-10	1.62	10

Crack Path Obstacles and Inertia

Preliminary Take-aways:

HOMOGENEOUS TOUGHENING

- the presence of diamine hardeners did NOT improve dynamic fracture toughness, possibly due to the fact that the polymer chains did not have time to relax
- overall the trend noted in literature under quasi-static conditions of K increasing with amine harder density increasing does not appear to hold under impulsive loading

HETEROGENEOUS TOUGHENING

- secondary phase toughening is highly dependent on the interface, more so under dynamic conditions, functionalization could be used to try to improve interface properties
- the trend of toughness increase under quasi-static loading due to crack pinning and deflection does not as strongly hold under dynamic conditions
- crack speeds for quasi-static and dynamic conditions remained nominally identical

For more information, please refer to the following papers:

- A. Bellafatto, S. Pagano, M.I. Mendoza, K.A. Masser, G. Palmese, L.E. Lamberson
Diamine Hardener Homogeneous Toughening Investigations in Mode-I Dynamic Fracture, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, under review (2019).
- A. Bellafatto, S. Pagano, M.I. Mendoza, S. Santos, G. Palmese, L.E. Lamberson
Glass Particulate Heterogeneous Toughening of DGEBA in Mode-I Dynamic Fracture, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, in submission (2019).

Ongoing Work

*Moving toward additive manufacturing of matrix materials,
and tensile testing of PMC's and temperature/dynamic
fracture investigations*

Challenge: Poor toughness and small range of
properties in higher Tg resins.

*Collaborations with G.
Palmese Group at
Drexel University*

Thank You! | Questions?

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